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To cite this article: Agnieszka Antończyk *et al* 2025 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1337** 012009

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Characterization of cenospheres from two sources: Impact of sieving on structure, morphology and composition

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Abstract. Cenospheres obtained from fly ash industrial waste from two different locations (Cp from Poland and Ck from Kazakhstan) were horizontally sieved to produce a size-defined fraction, which was then characterised in terms of its structure and phases. Morphological inhomogeneities (Cp), defects in the spherical particles of the oversize fractions (Cp40 and Ck40), and destruction of the microstructures (Ck<40 and Cp<40) were detected using SEM. Size-identical undersize fractions of cenospheres with an average size of 29–34 μm (Ck<40 and Cp<40) were prepared by sieving. X-ray diffraction analysis confirmed the presence of a crystalline phase consisting mainly of quartz, mullite and calcite, with hercynite and anhydrite in the Ck<40 sample, and potassium aluminate oxide in the Cp40 sample. SEM-EDS mapping confirmed the predominant presence of potassium and calcium on the edges and surface defects of the cenospheres. The sieving process produced no significant changes in the FTIR spectra of the smaller cenospheres size fractions compared to the input materials.

1. Introduction

Cenospheres are ceramic microspheres created as by-product during the combustion of coal in power plants. The fuel, i.e. coal for combustion in power plants, is selected based on the preferences of a given power plant; it can be hard coal, lignite or other additives not considered by power plants or combined heat and power plants. Studies show that during the combustion of hard coal we get siliceous ash, while in the case of lignite we have to deal with a significant amount of calcium oxides, which prevents the formation of cenospheres [1].

As the temperature increases during combustion, the highly dispersed mineral substance melts [1]. Materials, i.e. aluminosilicates, clay minerals, minerals with high SiO_2 content transform $T = 1200^\circ\text{C}$. Those mineral particles that form glassy phases or eutectic mixtures assume a spherical shape. Gases that were released during combustion form a cavity inside the spherical form. Due to the prevailing high temperature in the combustion chamber, the outgoing waste gases and ashes are activated, i.e. a rapid cooling process to consolidate the spherical form. The cenospheres contained in the gas and ash storm settle on special filters (e.g. electrostatic

precipitators), where they are then precipitated and pneumatically transported to retention tanks. This makes it possible to separate the ash and slag fractions, which settle to the bottom. The collected material is then cleaned in droplet chambers by rinsing with filtered water. The final stage is drying in gravity dryers and segregation based on specific gravity. Due to the increasing use of cenospheres, they are extracted all over the world, including the US, Russia, Kazakhstan and India [1-3].

Cenospheres is a light-coloured, gas-filled spherical particle composed of two main components: a solid outer shell and a gas-filled core. The shell is made of amorphous aluminosilicate material, although it may also contain crystalline inclusions. This shell mainly features a dominant glassy (vitreous) phase alongside a crystalline phase. The glassy portion is primarily composed of silicon and aluminium oxides, with smaller amounts of iron and calcium oxides. The crystalline part includes minerals such as quartz and mullite, with minor quantities of hematite and magnetite. While other compounds may also be present, they typically appear only in trace amounts. Additionally, cenospheres may contain traces of heavy metals like copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), and chromium (Cr). The general chemical composition intervals of cenospheres (C) are presented in Table 1. The interior of the cenospheres is mainly filled with CO₂ and N₂. During drying, the gypsum, portlandite, and brucite present in the cenospheres can transform into more stable forms, such as carbonates, primarily calcite, dolomite, and possibly magnesite by absorbing carbon dioxide from the air [1-4].

The grain size of cenospheres is in the range of 0.125 - 0.500 mm (93%). The largest fraction by volume is 0.250 - 0.300 mm. In contrast, fractions above 0.500 mm (6%) and less than 1% are dusty, i.e. the finest fractions. The desired phases can be obtained by using an automatic sieve shaker with a selected sieve [1-2].

Their spherical structure and gas filling allow cenospheres to participate in other materials as an ultralight filler. Their bulk density is only 0.45 g/cm³. In addition, thanks to their low thermal conductivity coefficient, they have thermal insulation properties.

They have found use in sectors as automotive (components like body panels, anti-corrosion coatings, and power cable insulation), protection of radioactive waste, aerospace and medical industries, as well as in the manufacturing of detonators. The use of cenospheres as a filler, will produce a composite material with unique properties. Doped polymer composites are currently used in components that constitute implants, e.g. nails and screws that fix damaged bone struts during fractures. They can also be used as an initial scaffold for bone, where the matrix will begin to degrade after some time [4-7]. The primary industrial benefit of aluminosilicate use lies in lowering production costs, while simultaneously enhancing the properties of the final product [1-4].

The main objective of the work was to perform basic material characterization of cenospheres from two different natural sources and to assess structural, phase, elemental and size changes that may occur after the sieving process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The spherical aluminosilicates samples (cenospheres) from two different locations were used. The cenospheres from Kazakhstan (pristine Ck sample) source from GRES-2 power plant and cenospheres from Poland (pristine Cp sample) source from Enea Bioenergia Sp z o.o. power plant. Ck and Cp cenospheres were cleaned in an ultrasound bath in demineralized water and dried at 50°C for 24 hours. The horizontal siever (Multiserw Morek, LPzE-2e, Marcyporeba,

Poland) with certified sieves with an average mesh size of 40 micron were used for the under-sieving fraction preparation (Ck<40, Cp<40) and the sieve fraction (Ck40, Cp40) of the cenospheres.

2.2 Characteristic methods of the cenospheres

Surface morphology were taken using a JEOL JSM-7610F Plus scanning transmission electron microscope (JEOL, France). The samples were attached to the metal targets and coated with a gold thin film to avoid electrical charging during the observation. An accelerating voltage of 15 kV and a secondary electron detector (SEI, LM) were used in the measurement.

Particle size distribution measurements were performed using a Horiba laser scattering particle size distribution LA-950 (Horiba, Japan) in distilled water. Particle size analysis was performed with refractive index values of 1.540 for samples and 1.333 for distilled water.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were measured using the X-ray diffractometer Rigaku Ultima IV (Rigaku, Japan, CuK α radiation, NiK β filter, scintillation detector, Bragg-Brentano arrangement) in ambient atmosphere under constant conditions (40 kV, 40 mA, scanning range 5-60° 2 θ , scanning speed 3.5°/min).

The chemical composition was obtained from elemental analysis using X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) Supermini200 wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (RIGAKU, Japan). Powder samples were placed freely into polyethylene cups with thin Mylar films.

The FTIR spectra of cenospheres samples were measured by ATR (Attenuated Total Reflectance) technique on a single-reflection diamond ATR crystal. The FTIR spectra were collected using FT-IR spectrometer Nicolet iS50 (ThermoScientific, USA) with DTGS detector. The measurement parameters were the following: spectral region 4000-400 cm⁻¹, spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹; 64 scans; Happ-Genzel apodization.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Cenospheres morphology and particle size

The diameter and morphology of the cenospheres was evaluated using SEM (See Fig. 1a), 1b)). The particle size evaluated by the average value of mode diameter (d_m) and particle size distributions are shown in Fig. 1c) and 1d).

Firstly, the diameters of the individual cenospheres were characterised. Cenospheres Cp exhibited the highest average diameter in the 156 - 144 μm range. They did not exhibit a spherical shape. Their surface consisted of deep cavities containing very fine spherical particles with a diameter of 2 - 10 μm . Similar-sized particles were embedded in the surface of the original cenospheres (i.e. they formed the surface). Particle size distribution analysis (Fig. 1d) confirmed the presence of two size fractions in the Cp sample volume, detecting values of 6.7 μm (d_{m1}) and 174.6 μm (d_{m2}). Cenospheres Ck were spherical in shape with a wrinkled surface formed of very fine, non-spherical particles. The diameter of individual cenospheres reached 66 μm . Occasionally, Ck cenospheres formed from large cavities revealing the internal structure of the cenospheres. The Ck sample contained fragments of walls from what were probably originally large cenospheres, as evident in the particle size distribution (Fig. 1c), where they appeared as an agglomeration maximum at values of approximately 10 - 20 μm . These values correspond to the wall thickness of the cenospheres.

Figure 1. SEM images of the Ck, Ck40, Ck<40 samples (a) and Cp, Cp40, Cp<40 (b) samples. Log-normal particle size distributions of the Ck, Ck40, Ck<40 samples (c) and Cp, Cp40, Cp<40 (d) samples.

Cenospheres sieving contributed to size separation but also structural destruction of cenospheres. The supersieved fraction of the Ck40 sample corresponds to the original particle size distribution with only a slight decrease in mode diameter (d_m) from $59.0 \mu\text{m}$ to $51.5 \mu\text{m}$, and the cenospheres retained their original morphology. On the other hand, in the sub-sieve fraction Ck<40 there was a significant decrease in the mode diameter (d_m) value to $29.9 \mu\text{m}$. There was a significant decrease in the presence of spherical particles in the sample volume. The cenospheres diameter which retained their original spherical shape reached $44.1 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, the Ck<40 sample was composed of cenospheres fragments of non-uniform shapes. A similar pattern of structural destruction was observed in samples Cp40 and Ck<40. In the case of the Ck<40 sample, however, it is noticeable that the cenospheres reach a thickness of about $10 \mu\text{m}$, which is lower than that of the Ck sample. There is a noticeably higher proportion of these walls in the sample volume, which form very fine fractions, and the particle size distribution suggests that they often reach sizes smaller than $1 \mu\text{m}$. It can be hypothesized that Ck cenospheres are much more fragile than Cp cenospheres and thus subject to mechanical breakage induced by the shaking of the sample on the metal sieving machine. This can be attributed to the difference in chemical composition, with Cp cenospheres having a higher Fe_2O_3 content and a lower SiO_2 content (Table 1). The Ck40 cenospheres diameter which retained their original spherical shape reached $57.2 \mu\text{m}$ which is in relative agreement with the Cp40 cenospheres, which reached an average $58.0 \mu\text{m}$.

3.2 X-ray diffraction phase and structural analysis

Figures 2a and 2b show XRD patterns of Ck, Ck<40, Ck40 samples and Cp, Cp<40, Cp40 samples, respectively. The wide band, observed in XRD patterns, in the 2θ range between 17 – 32 indicates the presence of amorphous phase in the cenospheres samples.

Figure 2. XRD patterns of the Ck, Ck40, Ck<40 samples (a) and Cp, Cp40, Cp<40 (b) samples.

The samples Ck and Ck40 showed very similar XRD patterns. The main crystalline phase in the samples Ck and Ck40 was mullite $\text{Al}_{4.54}\text{Si}_{1.46}\text{O}_{9.73}$ (M; PDF card No. 01-079-1456). Another crystalline phases such as quartz SiO_2 (Q; PDF card No. 01-083-0539) and calcite CaCO_3 (C; PDF card No. 01-072-1937) were identified as admixtures in samples Ck and Ck40. The XRD pattern and also chemical composition in Table 1 of sample Ck<40 was very different. Quartz (Q) was identified as pre-dominant phase while mullite (M) secondary phase. The calcite reflections (C) were more intense, which was also confirmed by XRF analysis (Table 1). Additionally, two new phases were observed in XRD pattern: hercynite or ferrite spinel FeAl_2O_4 (H; PDF card No. 01-071-4915) and anhydrite CaSO_4 (A; PDF card No. 00-043-0606) [1].

Table 1. Chemical composition (in wt. %) of the general cenospheres (C) and the experimental samples obtained from XRF analysis.

Samples	SiO_2	Al_2O_3	MgO	K_2O	CaO	Fe_2O_3	SO_3
C	50 - 65	19 - 42	<1	<1	<1	0.7 – 6.5	<1
Ck	56.2	26.7	1.3	1.4	6.8	3.5	1.7
Ck40	56.0	26.5	0.9	1.3	6.2	3.5	1.6
Ck<40	50.5	19.3	1.9	1.6	14.3	6.2	3.0
Cp	51.2	32.5	0.9	4.4	1.6	5.5	0.3
Cp40	50.7	30.1	1.0	4.5	2.2	4.8	0.6
Cp<40	54.4	32.3	1.0	4.2	3.4	5.6	1.3

The presence of mullite (M), quartz (Q), calcite (C) and potassium aluminium oxide $K_{0.67}Al_6O_{9.33}$ (P; PDF card No. 01-070-7115) was detected from the XRD patterns of Cp cenospheres obtained from Poland in Fig. 2b. However, mullite was the main crystalline phase present in all Cp samples. The presence of potassium aluminium oxide, mainly in Cp40 sample, is related to higher amount of K_2O (about 4 wt.%).

The results of XRF analysis of cenosphere samples are summarized in Table 1. All cenosphere samples have high SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 content. Their total content exceeded 80 % of the mass for all cenosphere samples except Ck<40(68 %). The samples Ck and Ck40 show very similar values of chemical composition expressed in oxides and also the values of their SiO_2/Al_2O_3 ratio are the same (2.10). All Cp samples show similar chemical composition (Table 1) and the values of their SiO_2/Al_2O_3 are in the range 1.58 – 1.68. The cenosphere samples from Kazakhstan (Ck samples) have low K_2O content (< 1.7 wt.%) and high CaO content (> 6 wt.%) as observed in Table 1. On the contrary, in the case of Cp cenosphere samples obtained from Poland have lower CaO content (variable from 1.6 wt.% at Cp to 3.4 wt.% at Cp<40) and higher K_2O content (> 4 wt.%). Sample Ck<40 has a very different chemical composition compared to other cenospheres samples. The biggest change is evident in the increase in CaO content (up to 14.3 wt.%).

Figure 3. SEM – EDS mapping of the Ck, Ck40, Ck<40, Cp, Cp40, Cp<40 (b) samples. In detail the elemental distributions of Ca (green colour) and K (brown colour) elements on the cenospheres surface.

Elemental mapping at the microstructural level by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS) - SEM-EDS mapping - was used to confirm the presence and distribution of the constituent elements in the microstructure of the cenospheres (Fig. 3). The analysis revealed that elements such as silicon (Si), aluminium (Al), iron (Fe) and magnesium (Mg) form the basic microstructure, or rather the smooth surface, of intact cenospheres. In places where defects were present, such as cavities, pore edges or fragments of cenospheres, the elements potassium (K) and calcium (Ca) were detected. In the case of the Ck cenospheres, Ca was predominantly present on the cenospheres edges and surface defects; in the case of the Cp cenospheres, it was K. These findings are in good agreement with XRF analyses when for both types of cenospheres (Ck and Cp), the concentration of these elements is highest in sub-sieved fractions (Ck<40 and Cp<40), where the most defective structures are found.

3.3 FTIR analysis

Fig. 4 shows FTIR spectra of Cp, Cp40, Cp<40, Ck, Ck40, and Ck<40 samples. The bands observed in the 1441–1417 cm^{-1} region correspond to the asymmetric stretching vibration (ν_3) of the carbonate group (CO_3^{2-}). Another peak associated with presence of carbonate group is in-plane bending mode (ν_2) near 874 cm^{-1} [8]. These findings confirming the presence of calcite as supported by XRD analysis.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra of the Cp, Cp40, Cp<40, Ck, Ck40, and Ck<40 samples.

A broad absorption band in the 1016–1030 cm^{-1} range is attributed to the valence vibration of Si-O-Si(Al) within the cenospheres lattice. This is followed by deformation vibration of Si-O around 874 cm^{-1} . In the case sample Ck<40, a weak band appear at 1008 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to valence vibrations in the bridging Si-O-Si(Al) bonds in the crystal lattice [9,10].

The bands at 796 cm^{-1} , further around 545 cm^{-1} for Cp samples and around 530 cm^{-1} for Ck samples represent Al-O bending vibrations and Fe-O stretching vibrations, respectively. Additionally, a minor peak at 778 cm^{-1} in the case of Ck<40 indicates the presence of quartz, which is also obvious from the XRD patterns [9].

As we can see from the FTIR spectra (Fig. 3), various valence vibrations of Si-O-Si(Al), Al-O or Si-O can be attributed to several absorption bands observed in the wavenumber interval below 950 cm^{-1} . Their positions and intensities are strongly influenced by the Si/Al ratio in the cenospheres structure, which is determined by the material's origin and processing method. It is evident from the spectra that there is a clear distinction between Cp and Ck samples. This difference highlights the heterogeneous nature of these materials, which are not pure substances but rather technical products with complex compositions [10].

Regarding the processing of samples by sieving to a smaller size fraction, there are no significant changes in the FTIR spectra compared to the input material.

4. Conclusion

Cenospheres from two locations Poland and Kazakhstan were processed by targeted sieving process. It was found that this process causes the destruction of the spherical particles, which in the sub-sieving fraction are formed with an average size of 29 – 34 μm . No significant changes in the FTIR spectra were detected compared to the original materials. Cenospheres are primarily composed of a crystalline phase consisting of quartz, mullite and calcite. Regarding to the origin materials, potassium or calcium is present in the structures, which are mainly detected in the cenospheres defects. The presence of calcite was confirmed primarily in sample Ck<40, indicating its occurrence when the internal structure of the cenospheres is disrupted. Calcite can crystallize on the surface of cenospheres, particularly as a result of carbonization processes or during wet separation followed by drying. Cenospheres composed of silicon, aluminium and iron oxides, which make the materials environmentally friendly and very well tolerated by the body. Therefore, they can be used as a filler in composites materials for example bone cements, polymer composites or as ceramic materials replacement.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690898>.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 “Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komensky Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of Czech Republic - MATUR” and CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000045 “Circular economy R&D Centre – CirkArena, The Operational Programme Just Transition”. Authors thank to L. Plesník for SEM micrographs.

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